

Soil Carbon Forms and Organic Matter Distribution in Arable Soils of Rigachikun, Northern Kaduna, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study was done in Rigachikun Kaduna, Northern Guinea Savanna and intended to investigate the carbon forms such as Organic carbon, carbon loss on ignition (LOI), Biomass microbial carbon (BMC) as well as organic matter distribution of the studied soils. A reconnaissance survey was carried out in the study location using the developed Digital Elevation Model (DEM). Soils were delineated into mapping units using the cropping land uses namely maize, cowpea and rice. In each of the cropping land use, three profile pits were sited giving a total of nine profile pits. Organic carbon contents of investigated soils were low and decreased down the horizon in all investigated pedons. This trend follows closely to organic matter which decreased in the same pattern with the values of organic carbon. Carbon LOI had a very highly significant relationship with BMC and OM, non-significantly correlated with Carbon/Nitrogen ratio, Clay, pH, K, Na and total exchangeable acidity (TEA). Biomass carbon had a negative and significant correlation with organic carbon, very highly and significant correlation with organic matter. BMC tolled the path of LOI in its relationship with other soil properties investigated. Also, all carbon forms (LOI, BMC, OC and OM) investigated exhibited high ($CV > 35\%$) coefficient of variation in all investigated locations except in pedon 3 of location B where BMC varied moderately and pedons 1 and 2 of Location C (Rice soils) where they all varied moderately ($CV > 15 \leq 35\%$). Generally organic matter content of the soils was very low resulting from continual use of crop litters in the feeding of farm animals rather than incorporating them to the soils. Soil

degradation, erosion and desert encroachment have also affected soil of north western Nigeria so immensely.

Keywords: Organic carbon, organic matter, carbon loss on ignition, microbial biomass carbon

Introduction

Soil carbon is known to be the biggest stocks of terrestrial carbon (Batjes, 1996; Jobbagy and Jackson, 2000; Lal, 2004). Across the globe, soil has the largest carbon storage capacity when likened to the carbon pools in the vegetation or atmosphere. Soil carbon is likely the most significant factor in soils, exhibiting great effects on soil properties. Carbon in the form of soil organic matter alters the physicochemical as well as the biological properties of the soils (Rice 2005). Kome et al., (2021) posited that soil carbon is a major index of soil quality and productivity serving as major mover of most soil activities or functions. It encourages nutrient retention, formation of micro-aggregate and good soil structure, soil buffering capacity, activity of microbes, moisture retention and infiltration rate (Hartemink et al., 2014).

Adhikari and Hartemink (2016) outlined the cardinal services and roles played by soil carbon in the ecosystem to include; regulatory (e.g., carbon sequestration, climate and greenhouse gas regulations); provision of services (e.g., food, water, fuel, fiber), cultural services (e.g., ecotourism and recreation), and also supporting services such as nutrient cycling. Batjes (1996), noted that the top 1m of the soils across the globe harbors about 2200 Pg of C, with about 2/3 of it, amounting to 66%, stored as soil organic matter. This volume of C is almost thrice that obtained in the atmosphere. Generally, soil carbon stocks are regulated by the balance of C inputs from plant production and outputs through decomposition (Schlesinger, 1977). Meanwhile, human activities on the soil, mostly agricultural practices and forest clearance for fuel and timber, have resulted to the emission of huge amount of the stored carbon into the atmosphere (Lal, 2010).

On the other hand, some human activities can significantly increase soil carbon sequestration, which include; enhanced farming activities such as addition of biochar (Ouyang et al., 2014), incorporation of crop residues (Han et al., 2018), and conservation tillage (Olsen et al., 2013, Moussadek et al., 2014, Omara et al., 2019). Despite many anthropogenic activities, many biophysical factors affect soil carbon storage and its mode of distribution in the soil. Generally, soil carbon is available in three different forms, namely; passive, intermediate, and active (Xu et al., 2016). The active and intermediate fractions are found in the top 1 meter of soil and are often collectively known as labile (microbial biomass carbon) soil carbon (Trumbore 1997). The soil carbon available at this topmost surface of the soil is biologically available and more subjected to transformation at the soil surface (Cheng et al., 2015). The labile fraction is the smallest pool of soil carbon and is estimated at 250–350 Pg (Trumbore 1997). This fraction develops from dead decaying organisms and fresh organic residues with a turnover range of days to few decades. Also, the passive or

more dependable component of soil carbon (chemically stable in the form of humus) is often accumulated below 1 m and is not easily available to microorganisms for decomposition (Trumbore 1997).

The subsoil contains the highest volumes of soil carbon and is not easily affected by changes in management practice and different environmental conditions when compared to top soil (Xu et al., 2016; Rumpel and Kogel-Knabner 2011). Constant check and quantifying soil carbon contents across different soil units from time to time are vital for the appraisal of spatial and temporal variations in soil carbon pools and fluxes. This is most vital in accessing the changes in soil productivity and its fertility levels, soil deterioration/amelioration, water quality, environmental degradation, hence necessitating the adoption of sustainable soil management practices for enhancing soil carbon storage and increased ecosystem services (Adhikari et al., 2019).

SOC is the foundation for soil productivity and fertility, means by which microorganisms derive their energy and regulator of climate and biodiversity (Dou et al., 2016; Li et al., 2013). Knowledge of the potentials and behavior of soil carbon is not only important in enhancing soil quality and sustainability of rangelands in Sub-Saharan Africa, but also mitigate climate change by offsetting CO₂ emissions (Hafner et al., 2012). Soil organic carbon is seen as an indicator of soil quality as it determines soil structure, nutrient retention and supports biological diversity (Chazdon 2008; Gil-Sotres et al., 2005). The reduction or loss of SOC could, therefore, lower soil fertility and consequently, lead to land degradation (Rounsevell et al., 1999). Today, it is absolutely necessary to give adequate attention to a better management of soil organic carbon to enhance soil fertility and productivity. As has been emphasized elsewhere, farmers and producers of tomorrow may need to not only farm soil judiciously but to also “farm carbon” (Lal, 2008). This study investigated different carbon forms and organic matter in arable soils of Rigachikun, Northern Guinea Savanna, Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Location

The study area is located on the Latitudes 10° 36' and 10° 60' N and Longitudes 7°25' and 7° 40'E respectively and in the north western Nigeria. Uyovbisere and Lombin (1991) noted that this region has a unimodal rainfall pattern and between 900 – 1300 mm per annum. The region also has a rolling but relatively plain slopes, having most of its elevations between 500 to 700 m, occupied by majorly sandy soils, which are critical in organic matter contents, degrading highly especially under intense precipitation and overgrazing (Obasi et al., 2022). The region experiences high intermediate annual temperature (28-32°C), brief rainy period and long dry season lasting from 6-9 months. The soil moisture and temperature regimes in the area are inferred to be ustic and isohyperthermic respectively (Soil Survey Staff 1975). Mean temperature often drops to 25°C – 28°C (June to September) usually during the rains and decreases to less than 20°C in the months between December and February (Gabasawa et al., 2017). Vegetation ranged from woodland to light forest which has been reduced to bare land due to uncontrolled tree felling for fuel as well as farming

activities (Carsky et al., 1998) while abundant short grasses (<2 m) are also available attracting nomadic cattle grazing (Sowunmi and Akintola, 2010).

Table 1. Geographic Coordinates of Research area in Rigachikun, Kaduna

Land Use	Location	Longitude	Latitude	Altitude (m)
Maize	1	10.614447	7.475940	609
	2	10.614585	7.476755	609
	3	10.613689	7.478127	605
Cowpea	1	10.614625	7.478230	607
	2	10.615250	7.477857	611
	3	10.716818	7.477228	610
Rice	1	10.615858	7.476001	612
	2	10.615727	7.475068	615
	3	10.613786	7.475203	609

Fig. 1. Map of study area showing sampling points

Existing Information on Soil

United States Department of Agriculture soil classification system placed soils of Northern Nigeria as Aridisols (Soil Survey Staff 1975). The soils of this region displays the properties of arid lands having very retarded moisture movement in the soil and slowly permeable, while greater volumes of its rains get lost through run-off (Fitzpatrick, 1980). These soils may have originated intense dry condition from wind-stored desert sands that accumulated over a long period of time. Also, some soils in the Northern Guinea Savanna found in states like; Kaduna, Katsina, Kebbi, Sokoto

and Zamfara of Northern Nigeria have been known to be ferruginous tropical soils (D'Hoore, 1965) and having mostly sandy texture, stretching through huge areas of land with minimal water-holding capacity and critical organic matter, nitrogen and phosphorus content, neutral or moderately acidic in pH and also having a low cation exchange capacity (Obasi et al., 2022). The region has the potentials to support mostly grain crops like maize, sorghum, millet, rice and wheat in the vast land mass that dominated the northern guinea savanna soils (Shehu et al., 2015).

Vegetation

Rigachikun is located in north western Nigerian with a vegetation of tropical Guinea Savanna. The increased anthropogenic influences such as nomadic cattle grazing, bush burning, and intense farming have apparently transformed the huge part of the original vegetation to bare lands (Obasi et al., 2022). Fitzpatrick (1980) stated that such vegetation of arid soils are always scantily distributed causing its surface to lay bare for long periods. Consequently, severe soil degradation situations arising from mostly wind erosion, leading to decline in soil fertility, and other serious soil and environmental degradation problems. However, few shrubs and grasslands are still available. The region has been occupied by some grasses such as; Elephant grass (*Pennisetum purpurem*), Giant star grass (*Cynodon plectostachyus*), Wild groundnut (*Calopogonium mucunoides*), butterfly pea (*Centrosema pubescens*), Goat weed (*Sida acuta*)(Obasi et al., 2022)

Socioeconomic Activities

Cereals are the most important staple food crop in this region (Muhamman and Gungula, 2006), grown by the people of Rigachikum whose major occupation is subsistence farming with food crops farming commonly practiced. Harris (2000) accounted that “In sub-Saharan northern Nigeria, farmers mostly grow millet, sorghum, groundnut, sesame and cowpea and in the Sahelian part they fall back to highly drought-tolerant crops such as millet and cowpea”. Meanwhile, the most marginal crops among them are sorghum and millet (both early and late varieties). Aregheore, (2005) reported that the most dominant crops grown by farmers in many northwestern states such as; Katsina, Kano, Kaduna, Sokoto and Zamfara are millet, sorghum, maize, cowpea, groundnut, and sometime soybean. Cereals are usually the dominantly farmed crops with one or few other crops mixtures. The cropping mixtures mostly practiced in the location may be; sorghum/groundnut; sorghum/cowpea; sorghum/millet/ cowpea and sorghum/millet (Muhamman and Gungula, 2006). Furthermore, millet and sorghum are usually planted on the same plot in most farmlands around Kano, Kebbi and Sokoto states. Millet are usually planted immediately after the first rain, while sorghum is inter-planted later after the rain must have become more intense and reliable (Mortimore, 1989). Asadu et al, (2004) stated that crops such as cowpea which covers the soil well may be brought into different cropping system such as crop rotation and mixed cropping.

Field Work

A reconnaissance survey was carried out in the study location using the developed Digital Elevation Model (DEM). Soils were delineated into mapping units using the cropping land uses namely maize, cowpea and rice. Three profile pits were dug in each cropping land use of maize, rice and cowpea depending on the identified soil groups, pedons were sunk in each of the delineated mapping units giving a total of nine profile pits. About 1kg samples were collected from the different horizons of each pedon at the different arable crop grown soils for carbon content and organic matter analysis as well as other soil physicochemical properties studied. Samples were carefully packaged and labeled and transported to the standard Soil Science laboratory of ABU, Zaria for analysis.

Laboratory Soil Analysis

Some physical and chemical properties of the soil were used as parameters for the study. Physical properties are: Mechanical analysis (particle size distribution), while the chemical properties are: soil pH, exchangeable acidity (Al^{3+} and H^+), exchangeable bases (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , K^+ , Na^+), ECEC, percentage base saturation, total nitrogen, available phosphorus, organic carbon, organic matter and carbon /nitrogen ratio. Their methods of determination are as follow: Particle size distribution was determined by hydrometer method using the procedure of (Gee and Or, 2002), Soil pH was determined in 1:2.5 soil liquid ratios in water and 0.1N KCl (IITA, 1979). Organic Carbon was determined using method described by (Nelson and Sommers, 1996). Total Nitrogen was determined using modified micro Kjeldahl method (Bremner and Milvaney 1982); Total available phosphorus was determined using Bray II method (Olsen and Sommers, 1982); Cation exchange capacity (CEC) was measured by repeated saturation using 1M NH_4OAC followed by washing, distilling and titrating (Soil Survey Staff, 1996). LOI was measured using the method of Schulte and Hopkins (1996). Biomass carbon was estimated using the method of Marumoto (1984).

Digital Elevation Model (DEM) Study

A digital elevation model (DEM) is a digital representation showing ground surface topography or terrain, mostly referred to as a digital terrain model (DTM). In this research, the DEM was derived from the contour lines of the topographic map of the study areas. Global Positioning System was used for ground truthing of the study area for recording of coordinates of the crop lands used for the study. Digital Elevation Model (DEM) was generated using a point data having the x, y, z coordinates arranged in a regular grid pattern. Furthermore, the point data grids were imported into surfer 21.0 software to produce the 3 Dimensional digital elevation model (Acker et al, 2003). Digital elevation model (DEM) is used by most GIS professionals to extract topographic information such as slope and aspect. With the DEM data for the study area, a grid file is generated in ArcView first, and then a slope file. The points of regular grids were now used to generate the Digital Elevation Model using Kriging interpolation Method (Pavlova, 2017). Coordinates readings

were thereafter launched to ArcGIS 10.5 platform and later linked with Google Earth for full identification of the crop land and its environs.

Statistical analysis

Coefficient of Variation (CV) was used to estimate the degree of variability existing among soil properties in the study site. Coefficient of variation (C.V.) ranked as follows; Low variation $\leq 15\%$, Moderate variation $>15\leq 35\%$, High variation $>35\%$ was used as outlined by Wilding, (1985). Correlation was done using SPSS software package.

Result and Discussion

Organic Carbon and Carbon Loss on Ignition (LOI)

Soil organic carbon (SOC) and carbon loss on ignition (LOI) of the studied soil are as shown in (Table 3). Organic carbon content of investigated soils were low and means recorded as follow; location A; 3.142, 3.193 and 2.926 gkg^{-1} ; location B, 2.044, 2.493 and 3.940 gkg^{-1} , location C, 3.460, 3.940 and 3.03 gkg^{-1} in their pedons 1, 2 and 3 respectively. The organic carbon all decreased down the horizon in all investigated pedons. This trend follows closely to organic matter which decreased in the same pattern with the values of organic carbon. Organic matter distribution took the following trends; Location A; 5.525, 5.505 and 5.044 gkg^{-1} ; Location B; 3.525, 4.300 and 6.793 gkg^{-1} . Location C; 5.960, 6.800 and 5.221 gkg^{-1} all in their respective pedons 1, 2 and 3. The high concentration of organic substances such as twigs, litter, dead decayed organisms on the surface of soils may be largely responsible for the higher organic carbon and organic matter on or near the surface of the studied soils. (SOM) has been used in different ways to describe the organic constituents of soil (Obasi et al., 2015; Obasi et al., 2019). Carbon loss on ignition (LOI) were highest at the surface horizons and decreased down the profile steadily in all investigated soils. Means Carbon loss on ignition were as follow; location A; 1.053, 1.064 and 0.990 gkg^{-1} ; B; 0.712, 0.830 and 1.249 gkg^{-1} ; C; 1.070, 1.320 and 0.812 g/kg in their pedons 1, 2 and 3 respectively. There was high variability ($CV > 35$) carbon loss in all investigated pedons of all locations except in location C pedons 1 and 2 where it was moderate ($CV > 15 \leq 35$).

Carbon LOI correlated highly significantly with BMC and Organic matter. It however has a negative and non-significant correlation with organic carbon, Avail. P, Ca, Mg and total exchangeable bases (TEB). Batti and Bauer (2002) noted that LOI method measures the organic-matter content of soils, but the change of the organic-matter content to a C basis may be tasking because the C content of organic matter may not be compatible and varies with vegetation type, degree of decomposition, age, and other factors. Thus, direct correlation between LOI and total C may be necessary for each soil type, geographic region, or land management practice (Konen et al. 2002). Previous researches indicated that LOI was a good predictor of total C, but with field verification necessary to optimize the conversion factors (Batti and Bauer 2002). Wright et al., (2008) used LOI method to assess total C in wetland soils of the Everglades. Soil total C measurement undertaken by Carbon-Nitrogen-Sulphur

analysis was confounded by the presence of CaCO₃, which exists in Everglades soils at widely variable concentrations. The LOI method was not impaired by CaCO₃ at any organic-matter content. The relationship between soil total C and LOI was excellent in soils with organic matter levels exceeding 400 g/kg. The present study scored OM values < 10 g/kg in all study locations and may be responsible for the negative and non-significant relationship between organic carbon and carbon LOI.

Fig. 2. Map of Study Area Showing Sampling Points and Contour Lines

Table 2. Means of selected soil properties

Locations	Clay gkg ⁻¹	pH	Organic C M. gkg ⁻¹	Avail . P mgkg ⁻¹	K	Na	Ca	Mg	TE B	TE A
Maize	102.5	5.97	3.525	2.83	0.0	0.0	5.8	1.5	7.48	0.95
	5				8	3	0	9		
	102.5	6.05	4.300	2.58	0.0	0.0	4.3	1.1	5.66	0.85
	5				8	5	5	8		
	137.5	5.88	6.793	1.63	0.0	0.0	4.2	1.2	5.61	0.85
	5				6	5	5	5		
Cowpea	90	6.04	5.96	2.32	0.0	0.0	4.2	1.2	5.56	1.20
					6	6	0	4		
	82.5	6.00	6.80	2.02	0.1	0.1	5.4	1.5	7.17	1.12
					0	1	5	1		

	110	6.07	5.221	2.02	0.1	0.1	3.6	1.0	4.97	1.05
					4	5	5	3		
Rice	107.	6.51	5.418	1.89	0.2	0.2	6.2	1.6	7.66	0.8
	5				9	1	0	7		
	80	6.27	5.503	2.19	0.1	0.0	6.0	1.6	7.96	1.45
					4	9	5	8		
	80	6.14	5.044	2.86	0.1	0.0	7.5	2.0	9.73	0.67
					1	5	3	3		

Table 3. Soil Carbon Distribution of Studied Soils in gkg^{-1} , BMC ($mgCkg^{-1}$)

Samples locations	LOI	BMC	OC	CNR	OM	LOI	BMC	OC	CNR	OM	LOI	BMC	OC	CNR	OM
	Pedon 1					Pedon 2					Pedon 3				
Location A: Maize															
A	2.340	8.729	6.983	7.98	12.04	2.594	8.650	7.781	7.99	13.41	1.729	5.760	5.187	8.00	8.942
AB	0.931	3.491	2.793	7.36	4.815	0.865	3.240	2.594	6.99	4.472	0.700	2.490	1.995	7.00	3.439
Bt1	0.670	2.217	1.995	7.00	3.439	0.466	1.750	1.397	7.02	2.408	0.540	2.000	1.596	7.00	2.752
Bt2	0.270	1.000	0.798	7.00	1.376	0.332	1.250	0.998	6.97	1.721	-	-	-	-	-
Mean	1.053	3.359	3.142	7.34	5.418	1.064	3.722	3.193	7.24	5.503	0.990	3.41	2.926	7.33	5.044
CV	85.51	88.15	85.56		85.57	98.16	91.12	98.14	-	98.12	65.20	115.9	67.27		67.26
Location B: Cowpea															
A	1.950	6.210	5.586	8.00	9.630	1.529	5.740	4.589	7.00	7.911	3.200	12.00	9.576	8.00	16.51
AB	0.532	1.770	1.596	7.98	2.752	0.930	3.100	2.793	7.34	4.815	0.798	3.550	3.192	7.00	5.503
Bt1	0.266	1.000	0.798	7.00	1.376	0.530	2.000	1.596	8.02	2.752	0.598	2.250	1.796	7.02	3.096
Bt2	0.103	0.250	0.199	7.11	0.343	0.332	1.250	0.998	6.98	1.721	0.400	1.490	1.197	7.00	2.064
Mean	0.712	2.308	2.044	7.52	3.525	0.830	3.140	2.493	7.33	4.300	1.249	4.823	3.940	7.26	6.793
CV	118.14	100.8	118.8		118.8	63.60	21.85	63.49	-	63.48	104.9	29.16	97.68		97.68
Location C: Rice															
A	1.463	4.870	4.389	7.99	7.567	1.610	5.300	4.772	8.01	8.227	1.652	7.340	6.607	7.01	11.39
AB	1.000	4.430	3.990	8.18	6.879	1.530	5.090	4.589	7.99	7.911	0.734	3.260	2.937	8.00	5.063
Bt1	0.837	3.140	2.512	7.00	4.331	1.468	4.890	4.405	8.01	7.594	0.551	2.070	1.652	7.00	2.848
Bt2	0.980	3.260	2.937	7.01	5.063	0.673	2.520	2.019	7.01	3.481	0.310	1.150	0.918	6.90	1.583
Mean	1.070	3.925	3.46	7.54	5.96	1.320	4.45	3.946	7.76	6.80	0.812	3.46	3.029	7.48	5.221
CV	25.41	24.55	25.42		25.42	32.98	30.35	32.78	-	32.78	72.25	67.23	83.45		83.45

LOI = Carbon Loss on Ignition, BMC = Soil Biomass Carbon, OC= Organic Carbon, CNR = CN Ratio, OM = Organic Matter

Soil Organic Matter

Organic matter took after the organic carbon trend as it decreased in the same pattern with the values of organic carbon. Organic matter distribution took the following trends; Location A; 5.525, 5.505 and 5.044 gkg^{-1} ; Location B; 3.525, 4.300 and 6.793 gkg^{-1} . Location C; 5.960, 6.80 and 5.221 gkg^{-1} all in their respective pedons 1, 2 and 3. The high concentration of organic substances such as twigs, litter, dead decayed organisms on the surface of soils may be largely responsible for the higher organic carbon and organic matter on or near the surface of the studied soils. (SOM) has been used in different ways to describe the organic constituents of soil. Baldock and Skjemstad (1999) stated that SOM includes “all organic materials found in soils irrespective of origin or state of decomposition”. SOM consists of C, H, O, N, P and S. Included are living organic matter (plants, microbial biomass and faunal biomass),

dissolved organic matter, particulate organic matter, humus and inert or highly carbonized organic matter. Part of soil organic matter consists of carbohydrates, lipids and proteins that are abundant in fresh plant residues. These are rapidly metabolized, immobilized or decomposed (Adiaha, 2017). Lombin et al., (1991) noted that although there is a considerable variation in the nutrient composition of organic manures depending mainly upon the source, handling and management, the main nutrients supplied are N, P, K, Mg, Ca and a host of micro nutrients. The organic matter contents of locations A and B where rice and cowpea were previously grown were higher than those of Location B where maize was harvested although these differences does not entail much variation from the results. The huge litter deposits from rice husks and cowpea leaves may have contributed to these relatively higher values.

Adiaha (2017) reported that when organic matter is added to the soils, it does not only tackle bulk density challenges and increase water holding capacity of the soil, but also adequately enhance soil aggregate stability. Ander and Carter (1996) discovered that the quantity of water – stable aggregate (WSA) was usually a function of organic carbon content, and that labile carbon was usually positively correlated to macro-aggregate stability. Kay and Anger (1999) reported that a minimum of 2% SOM was necessary to maintain structural stability. Boix-Fayos et al., (2001) noted that a threshold limit of 3-3.5% SOM had to be reached to achieve increase in aggregate stability. However, all investigated pedons in the studied location all had their organic matter content far below the minimum organic matter requirement of soils as suggested by Kay and Anger (1999) and Boix-Fayos et al., (2001), who gave 2% and 3-3.5% (equivalent to 20 gkg⁻¹ and 30 – 35 gkg⁻¹) suggesting that organic matter will possibly pose serious challenge to the productivity of the studied soils acting as a limiting factor in the nutritional composition of the soils. Nguemezi et al., (2020) who worked on South-west Cameroun soils noted that any soil with organic matter content of < 2% will definitely encounter limitation challenge to soil productivity. The low organic matter in these soils may be linked to continual use of rice husks and other plant litters in the feeding of cattle and other farm animals which is a common practice in most parts of northern Nigeria. These crop residues, if they had been allowed to decompose on the soils, could have added substantial amount of organic matter to the soils. All the investigated locations showed high variability ($CV \geq 35$) except pedons 1 and 2 of location C where coefficient of variation was moderate ($CV > 15 < 35$) according to Wilding (1985).

Fig. 3. Relationship between divers Carbon Contents of Soil

Soil Biomass Carbon

Soil Biomass Carbon took the trend of organic matter and organic carbon in pattern of distribution across horizons (table 3; fig. 3). They were highest at the surface and decreased down the profile. The means distribution of biomass carbon follows thus; Location A; 6.10, 3.722 and 3.41 mg C kg⁻¹; location B; 2.308, 3.140 and 4.823 mg C/kg; location C; 3.925, 4.45 and 3.46 mg C kg⁻¹ in pedons 1, 2 and 3 of the respective locations. There was high variability (CV > 35) in virtually all the investigated soils except location B pedons 2 and 3 and location C pedons 1 and 2 where soil biomass carbon had moderate variability (CV >15 ≤ 35). More biomass were produced in Maize Plot pedon 1 (6.10 mg C kg⁻¹), followed by Rice Plot pedon 3 (4.823 mg C kg⁻¹) and Cowpea Plot pedon 2 (4.45 mg C kg⁻¹) while lowest occurred in Rice Plot pedon 1 (2.308 mg C kg⁻¹). The high variability of BMC in soil across crop utilization types could be attributed to differences in biomass production which influences mineralization, because it is accessible to micro-organisms. The rate of organic carbon input from plant biomass is generally considered a dominant factor controlling amount of microbial biomass present in the soil (Campbell *et al.*, 2000; Omeke *et al.*, 2016). Adeboye (2009) opined that BMC values are commonly high when large amounts of organic C are returned to the soil. Therefore, continuous and uniform supply of C from crop residues with low C/N ratio like cowpea would serve as an energy source for microbial activity in the soil (Omeke *et al.*, 2016). To a large extent, this would also contribute to soil productivity improvement. Omeke *et al.*, (2016) described soil microbial biomass as the living part of soil organic matter and composes less than 10 percent organic matter content in soil. However, it performs at least three important functions for plant production in an ecosystem; namely, labile source and sink of C, N, P and S, agent of nutrient transformation and pesticide degradation and acts as a cementing agent, promoting soil aggregation and structure (Salinas-Garcia *et al.*, 2002). Due to its dynamic character, microbial biomass

responds faster to changes in soil management, often before measurable changes occur in organic C and N (Carter and Rennie, 1982). A challenge in interpreting values of microbial biomass is the difficulty of knowing the attainable microbial biomass for a given land use and what level of microbial biomass may constrain production.

Table 4. Correlation of Carbon Forms with Soil selected Soil Properties

	LOI	BMC	OC	CNR	OM	Clay	pH	Avail. P
LOI	1,000							
BMC	0,906	1,000						
OC	-0,558	-0,669	1,000					
CNR	0,140	0,051	0,219	1,000				
OM	0,937	0,972	-0,657	0,163	1,000			
Clay	0,208	0,129	-0,185	-0,487	0,117	1,000		
pH	0,313	0,386	-0,126	0,623	0,445	-0,278	1,000	
Aval. P	-0,206	-0,201	0,053	-0,022	-0,090	-0,530	-0,100	1,000

Correlation Study of Soils

Carbon LOI had a very highly significant relationship with BMC and OM, non-significantly correlated with Carbon/Nitrogen ratio, Clay, pH, K, Na and total exchangeable acidity (TEA). It maintained a negative and non-significant correlation with organic carbon, Ca, Mg and total exchangeable bases (TEB). Biomass carbon had a negative and significant correlation with organic carbon, very highly and significant correlation with organic matter. BMC tolled the path of LOI in its relationship with other soil properties investigated. Organic carbon had a negative significant correlation with organic matter. It equally maintained a negative non-significant relationship with virtually all other properties investigated, except Avail. P and TEA where it had a positive and non-significant relationship. Organic matter correlated positively but non-significantly with other soil properties such as clay, Ca, Na, pH, TEB and TEA except Avail. P where it had a negative non-significant relationship.

Conclusions

Organic carbon content of investigated soils was low and means recorded as follow; location A; 3.142, 3.193 and 2.926 gkg⁻¹; location B, 2.044, 2.493 and 3.940 gkg⁻¹, location C, 3.460, 3.940 and 3.03 gkg⁻¹ in their pedons 1, 2 and 3 respectively. The organic carbon all decreased down the horizon in all investigated pedons. This trend follows closely to organic matter which decreased in the same pattern with the values of organic carbon. Carbon LOI had a very highly significant relationship with BMC and OM, non-significantly correlated with Carbon/Nitrogen ratio, Clay, pH, K, Na and total exchangeable acidity (TEA). Biomass carbon had a negative and significant correlation with organic carbon, very highly and significant correlation with organic matter. BMC tolled the path of LOI in its relationship with other soil properties investigated. This study has established that organic matter and organic

carbon content of soils of Rigachikun fall far below the threshold levels expected in most tropical soils. The causes of organic matter decline may be linked to environmental problems such as soil erosion and desertification as well as human activities such as overgrazing and bush burning. The situation has greatly threatened sustained agricultural productivity in many States of northern Nigeria including Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Jigawa, Kaduna Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Sokoto and Zamfara. These problems have led to serious damage to farmlands by the loss of organic matter, and the deterioration of soil structure which have significantly decreased crop yield in successive years.

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